

Trust as an Emotional Ability

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Abstract

This chapter discusses trust as an emotional ability, examines its limits in the context of psychopathology, and considers several normative implications from the perspective of phenomenological bioethics. First, it is argued that different forms of trust and related phenomena must be distinguished, together constituting what will be referred to as *trust-structures*: a wide-reaching, web-like texture that shapes our experience of ourselves, others, and the world. These distinct forms of trust are presented as structurally interconnected, such that changes in one reverberate through the others. It is further suggested that disappointments in one domain of trust may erode trust in other domains as well. It is also argued that individuals possess personal styles of entrustment—that is, they vary in how and in what they place trust and in how they respond to breaches of trust in one domain—resulting in differences in their *fiduciary capacities*. Second, the chapter elucidates how fiduciary capacities can be challenged and limited in the context of mental health. Third, it concludes with several considerations regarding these limits and the role of health care professionals in diminishing, sustaining, or extending them.

Keywords: trust-structures, fiduciary capacities, phenomenology of trust, emotional abilities, mental health, enacting trust

Introduction

In this chapter, I introduce the notions of trust-structures and fiduciary capacities to capture both the variety and the unity of different forms of trust, as well as their dynamic interplay. By fiduciary capacities, I mean the set of abilities that allow one to build and navigate structures of trust, enabling the pursuit and adaptation of the practical goals that matter most to oneself. Fiduciary capacities are what protect us from existential crises in the face of breaches of trust and thus play an important role in shaping our emotional experience. It is in this sense that I propose to conceptualize trust—understood as the conjunction of our fiduciary capacities and the involved trust-structures—as an *emotional ability* (sections 1–3). I then illustrate how certain mental health conditions may undermine precisely this ability, thereby revealing

important mechanisms in the genesis and maintenance of mental health issues (section 4). I conclude the chapter with considerations from the perspective of phenomenological bioethics, exemplifying the possible implications of fiduciary capacities for the treatment of people with mental health challenges—both in therapy and in their interactions with practitioners across broader health care contexts (section 5).

1. Varieties of trust

In his well-known book *The Divided Self*, R. D. Laing describes the anxieties following what he calls the “existential position” of a person lacking “ontological security” (Laing 1965, 39). An “ontologically secure person will encounter all the hazards of life, social, ethical, spiritual, biological, from a centrally firm sense of his own and other people’s identity” (Laing 1965, 39). However, an individual may not have developed such a firm sense and may even lack a stable perception of the permanence of things that most people take for granted. In such cases—schizophrenia being paradigmatic—a person may experience severe anxieties that prompt drastic attempts to navigate a threatening world and its accompanying affective experiences, so that “the world of his experience comes to be one he can no longer share with other people” (Laing 1965, 43). Others have likewise emphasized how the underdevelopment or erosion of trust—in oneself, in significant others, or in the social world more generally—can be profoundly detrimental to an individual’s emotional and psychological life (Herman 1991, Brison 2002, Fuchs 2015, Ratcliffe 2017, 2024).

This need not always take the drastic shape as observed in schizophrenia and described by Blankenburg under the label of a “loss of natural self-evidence (*Verlust der natürlichen Selbstverständlichkeit*)” (Blankenburg 2012). An individual’s ontological security can be shaken to varying degrees, depending on how trauma, challenging life events, or situational threats impinge upon their basic experience of stability, continuity, and safety in the world.

People may preserve a sufficient portion of their ontological security in the face of severe violence. They may realize what has happened to them and acknowledge the identity of things, of other people, and of themselves—even as the self feels wounded, disrupted, transformed, and alienated. And yet, they may find themselves unable to trust people other than their closed ones such as family and friends. They may even develop difficulties trusting anybody, while remaining ontologically secure. In fact, there is great variety in the ways our trust can be undermined and in how this affects our relationships with both our environment and ourselves. This can be observed across a range of diverse and challenging mental health conditions. These include depression, PTSD, various anxiety disorders, borderline personality disorder, autism spectrum disorder, vulnerable narcissism, and eating disorders, among others. Although such conditions may significantly overlap in their clinical manifestations, they differ greatly in how difficulties in enacting specific forms of trust figure in the lived experience of those struggling with psychological challenges. To give a few examples:

It makes a difference whether you feel a general mistrust in others because you have been severely traumatized by someone else in PTSD or because you may feel self-conscious about your body and how it is perceived by others in eating disorders.

Trust and mistrust figure yet differently across anxiety disorders, where sometimes the mistrust can be both directed at the circumstances activating fears and at one's affective process, as it is the case in panic attacks. This felt lack of trust or security may have more similarities with the kind of "bodily doubt" (Carel 2013) that can arise in the context of physical illness than with the mistrust in other people observed in vulnerable narcissism.

However, a lack of self-confidence or trust in oneself may be closely related to, or translate into, mistrust of others—something that can be paradigmatically observed in borderline personality disorder. How easily a lack of self-confidence can also strain trust in other people might be illustrated, not least, by cases of bodily doubt in the context of physical illness, impairment, or geriatric healthcare. Where a person is highly dependent on others, questions

about their reliability arise more frequently and are more salient, which may result in doubt or mistrust. Small encounters that may seem irrelevant to caregivers can be perceived by the person receiving care with much greater sensitivity, as subtle cues in the caregivers' behavior often shape their reflections on others' reliability and trustworthiness.

What these few examples suggest is that different forms and dimensions of trust that stand in dynamic interrelation with one another need to be distinguished. I will now turn to what I call *trust-structures* in order to conceptualize these dynamic interrelations.

2. The architecture of psychological security: trust-structures

To characterize the notion of trust-structures, two sets of questions are most relevant:

(a) The first set of questions that springs to mind concerns the possible scopes of trust: In what can we actually put our trust? What are possible objects of trust?

(b) The second set of questions concerns the nature of trust: Is trust essentially an experience and if so, what kind—a cognitive act of thought, an affective act of feeling, or is trust rather of volitional kind? Or, is trust an attitude that may manifest in experience but need not necessarily do so? Is trust something we actively perform or passively happens? Is the individual the primary locus of trust, or should trust rather be conceived as a collective phenomenon—an interpersonal praxis that defines intersubjective interaction, rather than a merely individual endeavour?

Although these questions would merit detailed discussion—and have indeed given rise to extensive debates in the philosophy of trust—I will only offer a brief sketch of possible responses in order to illustrate how I employ the notion of trust-structures.

(a) I will begin with the possible scopes of trust. The obvious candidates are other people, a group one identifies with, the individual self, or God. But our pre-theoretical language in everyday life is usually quite permissive regarding the employment of the term. Apart from the obvious examples, we speak of trusting a bridge to hold or a car to be working. But even on a theoretical level, language seems to have become more permissive in the past years, specifically in the context of technological developments in artificial intelligence and machine learning. There are good reasons, however, not to use the term too liberally. Can we really trust a machine, robot, an algorithm, or a Large Language Model in the same way we trust a person? Probably not (Schmidt & Loidolt 2023). And yet, our reliance on these entities—that are not mere things but could be argued to show some degree of agency (Floridi 2025)—betrays that whatever we may call the attitude we take towards them, it is one that resembles trust in many ways.

As will become clearer in what follows, the notion of trust-structures that I propose is intended to sidestep the often scholastic debates about what should be included on the list of possible objects of trust. The point is that many phenomena—such as our relationships with smart robots, but also with tools and other things—that merely resemble trust can nonetheless be so deeply intertwined with more paradigmatic forms of trust in our psychic lives that a conceptually strict focus on trust risks excluding important aspects of our trusting activities and habits.

This will become clearer if we consider three forms of trust that are relatively widely acknowledged: trust in other people, trust in the world, and trust in ourselves. I start with the first of the triad, as it is arguably the most paradigmatic form: interpersonal trust. The narrowest approaches to trust will typically accept that other people are what trust is concerned with.

To give an example from phenomenology, consider the following proposal: “trust only finds its fulfilment in a possible other, and most profoundly, in a person or community of persons” (Steinbock 2014, 201) and “at its core [trust] is oriented toward the other as a creative ‘center’

of acts” (Steinbock 2014, 202). By trusting, we expose ourselves to the freedom of another person. But isn’t this something that is true for any form of interaction with others? What is the criterion for a trusting relationship with another person?

It has often been emphasized that the possibility of *betrayal* is what characterizes trust towards others. Steinbock objects, however, that at least the trust-*experience* cannot be *about* possible betrayal, as this would put worry and concern at the heart of trust. Yet, this would be odd, given that when we do trust wholeheartedly, we precisely do not linger on the possibility that the other may not stand up to their word. When we trust genuinely, we feel secure despite the possibility that the other may not be trustworthy at all. This is why Steinbock’s alternative suggestion doesn’t work either: vulnerability (Steinbock 2014, 206f.; cf. Baier 1986). It’s true that we expose ourselves in trust and this makes us vulnerable, but when we trust, our thoughts do not necessarily revolve around this vulnerability, not even as an *accepted* vulnerability (Baier 1986). Moreover, vulnerability—just as exposition—is inherent to any interaction with others. While it is true that, in relying on others, trust adds to our vulnerability, it’s not the case that our trust experience thematizes this vulnerability.

Quite to the contrary, I like to suggest that trust is a transformation of our *felt* vulnerability. When we genuinely trust, we are precisely *not* concerned with the possibility of betrayal by the other. We don’t forget that, when we put trust in others, it could be betrayed, but this possibility remains *unthematic*. The deeper trust runs, the more our concerns about betrayal are pushed to the *margins* of consciousness, to use Gurwitsch’s topography of consciousness (Gurwitsch & Embree 1974).

We might then say that the trust experience is such that the question of possible betrayal is best understood as bracketed, the trustworthiness of the trustee un-questioned in the sense that it is not yet decided though treated as if, as a question, it didn’t matter (cf. Nguyen 2022). On this understanding, the possibility of betrayal is quite literally out of question, but it is not negated or “*durchgestrichen*” (Husserl 1966, 27), either. When our trust gets disappointed, we may not

be able to believe it and say things like “I would never have thought this of you”, and yet it is not like the possibility of betrayal came as a complete surprise, as something that is unthinkable. In fact, trust betrayal is always thinkable, it’s just that it is typically not thought. From all this, I take it that in trusting we are indeed vulnerable to betrayal; yet the very experience of trust, at least pre-reflectively, renders this possibility unthematic, putting it out of question so that it does not affect us as long as we remain in trust.

This is particularly evident in our pre-reflective interactions with the social environment, in which we might enact a form of interpersonal trust that need not be directed at specific individuals. In fact, Ratcliffe, drawing on Løgstrup, emphasizes that every intersubjective encounter involves both exercising some control over others and exposing oneself to their control, such that trust is our default attitude toward people in general (Ratcliffe 2017, 147). Walker similarly defines default trust as the unreflective expectation that strangers will behave acceptably, reflecting reliance on the normative order and safety of our shared environment (Walker 2006, 84). Thus, the object of trust here is less a particular person than the social world we inhabit.

This brings me to the second form of trust: trust in the world. If we accept that one can sustain a trusting relationship not only with particular individuals but also with people in general or with the social environment, then doesn’t it follow that speaking of entrusting the world itself may likewise make sense?

In the literature, we find many proposals of a general trust that is concerned with the contexts in which we move that, while being shaped interpersonally, are not reducible to the spontaneity of specific people. Luhmann (1979) has famously pointed out that trust functions as a sort of complexity reduction: If it weren’t for us to trust people, things, and processes, we would end up being overwhelmed by having to consider all possible outcomes of a situation.

Phenomenologists in particular have emphasized, in different ways, how deeply the phenomena of reliance and taken-for-grantedness that accompany trust are entrenched in our experience of

the world. For instance, Husserl maintains that we generally operate in a mode he famously termed *ur-doxa* (Husserl 1977, 241ff.; cf. Husserl 1966, 1976; Fuchs 2015). This refers to the tacit acceptance of what is given in perception as evident for navigating the lifeworld, such that it is not questioned unless counter-evidence arises. *Taking-for-granted* (or *taking-as-a-given*) is thus the primary mode, out of which doubt and critical questions of trust only become possible in the first place.

Similarly, Fazakas and Gozé (2020) highlight Merleau-Ponty's notion of *perceptual faith* as a mostly unthematic kind of trust that presents the transcendental ground or soil through which we come into the position to interact with the things of the world to begin with.

Another example is de Warren's (2020) interpretation of Heidegger's existential analysis of human being (*Dasein*) and his description of being-in-the-world as involving a fundamental familiarity (*Vertrautheit*) with the world. For de Warren, familiarity with the world is not only a form of relying on and being intimate with the world but also involves a "primordial trust in the world" because our "openness into the unknown" (de Warren 2020, 24) is at the same time an exposition: we give ourselves over to the world and its meaningfulness.

Endress (2010) distinguishes between a pre-reflective, functioning (*fungierend*) form of trust and reflective trust. As he notes, functioning trust operates in an unthematic manner and tends to grow stronger the more we enact it – so long as it is not disrupted by events in the world. If we pursue our personal concerns, taking certain things for granted, while focusing on our practical goals, functioning trust both endures and continually reaffirms itself. The more meaningful goals we manage to achieve in the world, the more we trust it. Reflective trust, by contrast, is the kind of trust we adopt through deliberation and evaluation of a situation. Interestingly, the more we enact this form of trust—that is, the more we consciously reflect on it, seek to justify it, and make decisions about it—the more it tends to diminish.

The variety of these examples point to a general mode of trust that guides us as we interact with others and the world, one that may also be said to refer *to oneself*, given that we ourselves

contribute to how these encounters run. If we trust the interaction with someone this involves a sort of reliance on or confidence in our own capacities. When we devote ourselves to the things that matter to us, care for others, and pursue our goals, we inevitably encounter a range of challenges across various social contexts. Some of these challenges test us more than others, and at times, they may overwhelm us. Nonetheless, we generally move through life with a degree of confidence that we can overcome obstacles, resolve conflicts, and manage the tasks at hand. We rely on our emotions to indicate not only what is important to us but also what we take a situation to be (Bortolan 2024), and we trust our ability to draw the right conclusions from the facts available to us (Govier 1998). We trust that our body and mind will not fail us as we set about our work.

Our entire engagement with life is, by and large, sustained by what Husserl described as a kinaesthetic “I can” (Husserl 1952, 257)—a sense of agency and sense of possible movement that pertains not only to bodily activities but also to our thinking and feeling. When we trust ourselves, we feel that we can steer and orient our thinking in the ways relevant to our cares and concerns. To trust ourselves is to trust in our capacity to take a stance toward things in a way that is meaningfully our own. This idea can already be found in Stoic philosophy: although we are entirely subject to fate in external matters, the Stoics believe we are free in the formation of our judgments, insofar as these are fully “up to us” (*eph’ hēmin*) (Epictetus 2008, Discourses, I.1).

Whether we are truly such self-sufficient epistemic agents, entirely independent of our social contexts, is dubitable. What I wish to suggest, however, is that self-trust is marked by a sense that our experience—our perceiving, feeling, and thinking—unfolds in a way that is faithful to our individual way of being, our identity. When we trust ourselves, we have the sense that the positions we take on life are *up to us* as the concrete persons we are, and that we can rely on the affective and practical abilities that underpin our capacities for forming judgements. Surely, this sense is typically not a prominent feeling at all times in our experience of the world. It

comes in degrees, is context-dependent, and volatile. In fact, it probably is the most salient when it is absent, and we painfully lack the self-confidence in a certain domain of life (or life in general).

Having sketched trust in others, trust in the world, and trust in oneself, the question arises as to whether there are not better words than trust for the phenomena mentioned. Wouldn't it be better or at least possible to speak of confidence in oneself, the social environment, and the world in general? Aren't we dealing with a kind of faith, security, safety, or feeling of being at comfort or home? Terminological choices on these matters may vary and it seems like different approaches remain possible. However, like other phenomenologists (e.g. Ratcliffe 2023, de Warren 2020), I suggest that we stick with the trust-label even in those cases that are not directed at concrete other persons. Although in these cases trust does not necessarily refer to the spontaneity of a specific agent, entrusting oneself still is intrinsically *relational*, an interaction with *otherness*. And, while feeling betrayed by a concrete other is certainly a specific experience, it doesn't strike me as a categorical mistake (neither conceptually nor phenomenologically) to say that I feel betrayed by the world or a given environment. Certain contexts promise certain possibilities and securities, afford our trust, but then disappoint us. A system can let us down.

(b) Having argued for a plural understanding of possible trust-objects, I now want to address the second set of questions that concern the nature of trust compartments and briefly sketch my position in this regard. The view I propose here assumes that trust, beyond having different possible objects, also varies in its genesis, sustainment, and—most importantly—manifestation. At times, we may trust someone we meet for the first time almost instantly. In other cases, trust emerges only through a prolonged process of interpersonal familiarization—one that may involve doubt, disappointment, anger, debate, and gradual reconnection—and crystallizes against a background of established mutual reliability within limited domains. Trust may also

appear as an affective dimension of a broader sense of attachment to another person, where it is experienced as an aspect of warmth, security, and support.

In other times, trust is a simple fact that remains silent as long as it isn't tested or until we reflect on it. Someone asks you: Can you trust him? And reflecting, it just takes a second to confirm. In such a case, trust is present in reflection in the form of the impossibility of doubt, where even possible counter-evidence will be blocked and alternative explanations will be sought. Trust in such cases is like a pillar that is tested by the structural engineer only to be determined quickly as strong enough to carry the whole building. Reflection of this kind is not the same as a reflective evaluation, where different bits of information are taken together to ground a justification, but rather the simple inquiry of whether one *feels* the kind of trust that is asked about. The feeling is generated by trying—if only in abstraction—to put a person in doubt and it is the immediate failure of such an attempt that provides the security.

In yet other cases, we may come to the conclusion that a person—objectively speaking—deserves to be trusted and nonetheless we find it difficult to adopt a trusting attitude, requiring further assurances which, with each one given, make the whole thing resemble more an episode of lack of trust or even mistrust. This can be the case if a person is generally insecure, anxious, and overly cautious. In such cases, the establishment of trust may require an *active* effort, where trust in another person needs to overcome and silence a loud background of general self-doubt and skepticism toward the world. And yet, even when trust needs to be volitionally and effortfully enacted against tendencies of avoiding any psychological dependency on others and desires for control, we can speak of trust—even where little doubts may pop up uninvitedly in a person's head.

My point is thus that interpersonal trust may look different against an insecure individual's affective background than in a person who is generally self-confident and feels at home in the lifeworld they inhabit. While possibilities for trusting others may be seriously diminished and completely eradicated in extreme cases, I think it is important to understand that acts of trust in

these contexts have their own modes that have a stronger active character than in contexts where trust is not only more generously given but also occurs in a more passive and automated way. It is worth further describing these last cases where single acts of trust are sprouting out of a root of generally felt safety. What I want to suggest is that sometimes trust is not so much felt in terms of feeling being held or guarded by a trustworthy environment and benevolent others that create a sense of security. Rather, security is felt in terms of a vital openness and curiosity, a desire to know or to get in touch with unknown others and the new. To illustrate the distinction I want to make: We may feel secure *either* because we are shielded from being touched by the new and unknown through a safe social context, *or* because we trust that being touched by the new and unknown will not harm us. The joy of curiosity harbors a sense of being safe, allowing us to turn to things that may well surprise us in the first place.

As a final example of the variety of trust-experiences, I would like to point to the fact that we should refrain from reducing trust to the comportment or experience of the individual that interacts with the world. As has been emphasized by some, trust—rather than individual attitude—is best understood as a social practice that is developed, established, and sustained through the interaction of different persons (Hartmann 2011). On this view, the locus of trust is not to be seen in the individual but—as a distributed phenomenon—in the collective. While I believe that such positions get something right in emphasizing that individual trust-experiences are typically embedded in and—on a general level—scaffolded through social contexts, I wouldn't want to reduce all acts of trust to shared practices, either.

To conclude this section, the trust-structures that feature in the architecture of our psychic lives spread out across our different relationships with self, others, and the world. They pervade our cognitive, affective, and conative orientations, cannot be reduced to any of them, and have multiple objects (de Warren 2020, 33). They involve both active entrusting and passive coming to trust; at times, they are intentionally directed toward specific objects or processes, while also

consistently shaping the broader horizon and background of our experience of the world. They also involve phenomena that could also be termed confidence, faith, reliance, security, assurance, and so forth. While some may distinguish them conceptually from more paradigmatic forms of interpersonal trust, I wish to emphasize that they are phenomenologically and psychologically intertwined with the latter. Hence, no matter what we call them, it should hardly be controversial that they are deeply and dynamically interconnected in various ways with the more acknowledged paradigmatic forms of interpersonal trust. Our self-confidence and faith toward the world are shaped by the social environments we encounter, and at the same time, they determine how we approach others. If we feel we cannot trust other people, it will be more difficult to sustain trust in the world more generally. And, if we can't even trust ourselves, it will likely be more challenging to entrust ourselves to others to begin with. When we put our trust in other people, it is not some kind of act that emanates from a background of insecurity and doubt inaugurating an island of safety in a sea of total chaos in which nothing was taken for granted. Our interpersonal trust is rather embedded in a web of structures that hold us together in a world of abounding possibilities that make us tremble if we were to refrain from relying on anything that isn't as indubitably given as our own Cartesian cogito. I call the whole or totality of this fiducial branching trust-structures.

3. Trust as an emotional ability: fiduciary capacities

Trust-structures scaffold our psychic life. They are complex and web-like. Because they are multipolar we can confront ourselves with the challenges, threats, and dangers of living in this world. Because we enact different forms of trust when we interact with the world, we can live up to the many disappointments and betrayals we witness and undergo ourselves every day. When a friend lets us down and we lose trust in them, there may still be others in our social environment to whom we happily entrust ourselves and with whom we feel secure nonetheless.

Not every interpersonal disappointment—be it a betrayal, deceit or abandonment (de Warren 2020, 131, 146)—undermines our trust in other people in general.

By *fiduciary capacities*, I refer to an individual's ability to respond to breaches of trust—i.e., various forms of disappointment in life—in ways that do *not* destabilize their practical agency or their commitment to what they care about to such an extent that it triggers an *existential crisis*. Such a crisis is characterized by a breakdown in one's orientation toward practical goals, a loss of clarity about what is meaningful to oneself, and uncertainty about how, to whom, or to what one should entrust oneself. One reason we do not face existential crises after many disappointments in our everyday lives is because we have the fiduciary capacities to process or forget the way others have let us down, undermined us, the errors we committed, or the bad luck we have had.

While we may be emotional over the single incidents that probe our trust in ourselves, others, and the world more generally, when we possess the relevant fiduciary capacities, such tests will often bring about an increase in a different form of trust. My partner betrays me but my best friend is there in a way I hadn't anticipated. Of course, there had been trust in him before, but the experienced support realizes, concretizes, and thereby fortifies the trust I had in him. If my trust in him before was more of a hoping kind, a form of a reaching out, it is now more of a secure base, a ground that allows me to build hope to overcome the betrayal I underwent and to develop the self-confidence to master the challenging times of ending a relationship. As trust gets disappointed by some people but confirmed by others, the trust-structures that shape our lifeworld dynamically develop and get modified over time.

However, how we experience trust is not only dependent on trust-structures. It also depends on how we enact trust and on which sources of fiduciary support we orient ourselves. We may rely more on our friends than our family, on one friend rather than another, or we choose to lean on the familiar and trustworthy work environments with clear norms and expectations that provide a reliable and controlled atmosphere in which self-confidence can be maintained or extended.

For others, these fiduciary goods will be sought more in hobbies and related communities: the gym, the soccer club, or dancing school. In any case, I propose, when one part of our trust-structure ceases to provide hold, we tend to reach out to other pillars in the structure. Metaphorically speaking, this is comparable to an embodied praxis in which we need to retain our balance by shifting our weight from one foot to another.

I shall emphasize that fiduciary capacities, as I understand them, are not a simple quantity, as if we were dealing with a depletable mass. Certainly, our fiduciary capacities will depend on the number of contexts in our lives in which we find ourselves in trustworthy atmospheres, with people we can trust, and a society characterized by norms and values that are shared with others and respected in the typical case. But our fiduciary capacities cannot be reduced to the ready-at-hand availability of a consumable resource, as if the fiduciary goods were just ‘there’. As the word ‘capacities’ suggests, we are dealing with something that is both a *potential* and a kind of *ability* to use of this potential, i.e., to realize it. This involves the practical ability to navigate between available fiduciary supports in a given situation, and not to cling onto specific familiar and trustful others that may not be present at all times.

To give an example, the homesick child that misses their parents or brothers and sisters still has to learn precisely this ability, which involves more than retrieving a ready-made fiduciary offer presented to an individual, namely the capability of generating new and expanding trust-structures. The homesick child learns to create bonds with unknown others or to deepen existing relationships, or, alternatively, to develop the kind of self-confidence necessary to withstand situations in which we cannot feel at home with the concrete others that surround us, without giving up what is important to ourselves. Imagine a child who just wants to read books, surrounded by little scrappers, having to stand its ground against mobsters no one can trust. Fiduciary capacities in my understanding thus also involve the capability of *building* the trust-structures needed—whether referring to trust in specific others or in oneself—rather than simply searching the lifeworld for fiduciary goods to be picked up.

A person with great fiduciary capacities thus is also someone who can bear significant disappointments of trust. One might also say that fiduciary capacities are an index for how much a person can take, the kind of breaches of trust that are tolerable and can be carried with oneself while one keeps moving, and a certain flexibility with regard to the kind of trust a person predominantly enacts at a given time. At times, we may feel uncertain about ourselves and not fully rely on our self-confidence; instead, we may entrust ourselves to the care or judgment of others. At other times, it may be more appropriate to refrain from seeking reassurance in others and instead live predominantly with trust in our own skills and capacities to handle the situation at hand. Yet in other times, the resilience of trust may arise more from a hopeful attitude toward the world and, more generally, from a trust that is teleologically oriented and actively performed, not necessarily motivated by certain facts, events, or ideas. We tend to turn to such forms of hopeful trust when we face hardship and challenges whose outcome we are unsure about—or when we are, in fact, fully exposed to the will of others or nature (e.g., in illness) and have no say in how things unfold. A person with great fiduciary capacities, I propose, is capable of switching between these modes and of developing new modes or objects of trust when a situation affords it.

It should be noted, however, that even a person with great fiduciary capacities will not be immune to just any social wound and trauma. Many people can endure a great number of incidents that undermine their trust and adapt to them by recalibrating their trust in the world. Still, severe threats, violence, and dismay inflicted upon an individual can annihilate trust in all humanity in one blow, as we have to witness, for instance, in the context of war and terror in human history over and over again (Frankl 2006, Walker 2006).

An example of little fiduciary capacities that do not necessarily require severe trauma can be identified in the context of people who tend to believe in conspiracy theories. Conspiratorial thinking provides a compelling lens through which to illuminate two key aspects of fiduciary capacities. First, fiduciary capacities and the trust-structures on which they are based are not

only defined by the kind of trust we enact—but, conversely, also by our scepticism, distrust, and the more explicit mistrust we embody towards certain people, communities, or aspects of social contexts. Conspiracy thinking is typically not characterized only by lack of trust and mistrust—for instance, in science, democracy, politics, the media, or in society—but comes with a hypertrophic if only *partial trust* in certain alternative communities and the ideas they consent to (Schmidt-Boddy et al., under review). To retain trust and a secure anchor in life, the individual needs to downplay any evidence against the conspiracy theory and thus typically engages in a sort of devaluation of any alternative source of trust that would be incompatible with the conspiracy theory. Scepticism in its various modes is the backside of trust—and vice versa. This holds true in general. Even we, who believe ourselves not to be victims of any ideology, will readily develop a skeptical and distrusting attitude toward those who appear to be such victims.

Second, what distinguishes a person with greater or lesser fiduciary capacities is, again, the flexibility or ability to change the trust-distrust distribution. Those who believe in conspiracy thinking often enact an inflexibility in this regard precisely to protect their ideological safe harbor. They cling to certain ideas or principles and reject evidence against them to be able to enjoy some psychological security, a phenomenon that can be well-described by Jaspers's (1919, 122) term of a "shell (*Gehäuse*)". By contrast, a person with greater fiduciary capacities will typically not have the need to engage in practices of mistrust to safeguard their trust-structures. Greater fiduciary capacities allow an individual to interact with those towards whom scepticism is felt. Someone with robust fiduciary capacities will be able to gather evidence, to correct and dispel first impressions, to give others credit, to show a leap of faith, and to be disappointed without having to fear an emotional crisis.

This brings us to the central aspect of fiduciary capacities that I ultimately want to highlight: they make trust a vital emotional ability. By *emotional ability*, I refer to the different individual skills and capabilities to feel, identify, engage in, sustain, or modify emotional experiences (cf.

Landweer 2022, Coelho, Vendrell Ferran & Stephan 2023). Fiduciary capacities make trust an emotional ability because they allow us to affectively deal with uncertainties, threats, disappointments, and challenges when we pursue our practical goals. They do so by providing sources of felt security where security is *not* a given fact. But to serve as such sources, they require agility, dexterity, and skill. That is what makes them an *ability* rather than a mere resource. To speak of trust as an emotional ability, moreover, means the following two things: first, trust is an emotional ability because if we have little fiduciary capacities, we are more likely to end up in emotional crises and of more severe kinds, as described by Laing in the example of schizophrenia mentioned in the beginning (cf. Ratcliffe 2017); second, fiduciary capacities and flexibility in enacting trust are reliant on several emotional abilities such that difficulties in coping with emotional experiences will undermine our fiduciary capacities. It is the second point I will turn to in the remainder of the article.

4. Fiduciary capacities in challenging mental health conditions

The repercussions of the erosion of trust-structures, given their complex and multipolar scaffolding of our psychic lives, can vary and manifest quite differently across mental health conditions, which I have sketched at the beginning of the chapter. In its remainder, my focus will be on borderline personality disorder (BPD), where lack of trust and insecurities are typically observed (Prete et al. 2023). In fact, they feature centrally in and define one of the core features of BPD: the struggle with interpersonal relationships and corresponding experiences of other people. Individuals with BPD tend to feel strong fears of being abandoned by others they care about and are concerned about losing their connection to them. They experience severe skepticism and doubts about the other's commitment to the relationship at stake, which, in peak times, can manifest as alarming mistrust in the relevant other. It seems plausible to assume that it is precisely these doubts and related feelings that trigger the often-mentioned

frantic efforts of individuals with BPD to prevent abandonment. Referring to de Warren, abandonment has been emphasized as one of the central modes of the disappointment of trust. It is in this sense that we might say that many of the symptoms of BPD revolving around the experience of attachment are the manifestation of a continuous crisis in the performance of fiduciary capacities.

In what follows, I present a few examples to illustrate how limitations in emotional abilities, together with the challenging emotional experiences they entail, can weaken fiduciary capacities.¹ I will focus on some of the core affective phenomena often observed in BPD that make up—formally speaking—central pillars of the emotional life related to it. It should be noted that these affective phenomena do not necessarily define the emotional life of someone with BPD at all times, but rather refer to distinct, albeit recurring, phases. Each of them, in itself, undermines fiduciary capacities, but taken together, they have a cumulative effect and significantly erode essential structures of trust.

Agitated bodies: Persons with BPD often experience higher levels of inner tension, bodily agitation, and affective arousal (Stiglmayr et al. 2008). To feel restless and ill at ease in one's own body is to sense the approach of a decision that may not fall in one's favor. Agitation, kin to worry and skepticism, is an inner drive toward fulfillment—yet one that is vague, without outline or path, and thus beyond anticipation. This “desperate vitality” (Stanghellini & Rosfort 2013) erodes self-confidence and an individual's sense of ability that is closely related to emotional experience (Slaby 2012). Because the need it voices is unclear, and over time it plants the deeper doubt of whether the unfolding process itself can be trusted.

¹ It's important to note that we are dealing with a vicious circle, given that a person feeling insecure and lacking relevant fiduciary capacities will ultimately tend to experience strong emotional upheaval. As I said before, my concern in this chapter is with the impact of emotional abilities on fiduciary capacities.

Emptiness and low self-esteem: Another set of different affective experiences and general mood in the background of persons with BPD concerns a pervasive sense of unfulfillment, purposelessness, and a vague and diffuse feeling of not being at one with oneself, a sense of not knowing who one is (Miller et al. 2021, Schmidt 2021a). It is fairly easy to see how a weak sense of identity and a painfully present low self-esteem can—or, in most people must—also amount to a decreased self-confidence and trust in oneself. Our sense of identity typically involves a tacit knowledge of the kind of capabilities we possess, what kind of situations we are able to navigate and solve, and how we can find out for ourselves what we need and want. Strong and abiding feelings of emptiness, however, give rise to an “affective self-construal” (Slaby 2012) that is associated with confusion, perplexity, and lack of self-reliability.

Mental pain: Emptiness and inner tension are far from being affectively neutral. They are associated with a sort of pain on the psychological or emotional level, consisting in the vague sense that one’s longing for connection with others and relationships with others in which one would feel at home with oneself is chronically and even hopelessly unfulfilled. The reasons for this are often attributed to the relevant others, such that the mental pain at stake goes beyond feelings of loneliness but involves a sense of abandonment, a mode of trust disappointment as emphasized. Ultimately, this will impact the perception of one’s practical agency as well. Endress (2010) highlighted that functioning trust is typically fortified as we succeed in yielding our practical goals—at least, to a certain degree. Experiencing an abiding or recurring pain about not being able to establish the kind of social connection needed grows into a sense that one is not capable of realizing what one deeply cares about, which further undermines the confidence in one’s practical agency.

Alexithymia, emotional flooding, and lack of control: Persons with BPD do not only experience challenging background feelings. In fact, it is often fully fledged emotional experiences, and

the situations shaped by them, that most disrupt the lives of those affected (Selby & Joiner 2009). This is not only because intense emotions can trigger escalatory behaviors, but also because of the characteristic patterns of emotional experience in BPD. One important aspect is that individuals with BPD frequently struggle to identify the specific emotions they or others are experiencing (Chaim et al. 2024). As a result, emotional responses to situations consistently introduce elements of uncertainty and insecurity. When emotions arise in individuals with BPD, they often build up rapidly without yet being identified and understood in their cause and direction, further increasing confusion and undermining confidence. When feelings have crystallized into a recognizable emotion, those with BPD still typically have difficulties in controlling or regulating them (Schmidt 2022). A lack of affective self-control undermines not only confidence in one's emotional abilities but also trust in one's practical agency. When feelings associated with a particular emotion persist, they can exert a profoundly alienating effect, leaving individuals with a sense of not fully understanding themselves. This erosion of self-understanding also weakens the self-trust required to allow emotions to serve as positive guides—that is, to treat them as epistemic sources for discerning what one wants and how one should act.

5. Treating people with limited fiduciary capacities: Implications for phenomenological bioethics

What can we learn from the insight that our psychic life is permeated by different trust-structures that are dynamically interrelated and form the backbone of our fiduciary capacities—that is, our abilities to process disappointment, betrayal, deceit, abandonment, uncertainty, and insecurity? I would like to conclude this chapter by offering a few considerations that exemplify possible answers to this question. Doing so, my aim is also to illustrate how an analysis of fiduciary capacities may inform ethical reflections on therapeutic practices.

From a phenomenological bioethics perspective, the analysis of fiduciary capacities makes us aware of the ethical importance of attending to the lived dynamics of trust and vulnerability that shape therapeutic encounters. It suggests that ethical practice cannot be reduced to rule-following or boundary management but must involve a reflective sensitivity to how trust is experienced, lost, and potentially renewed within concrete intersubjective relations—and beyond. Cultivating spaces where patients can re-establish or diversify their fiduciary capacities thus becomes an essential ethical task for therapy and care—*particularly* when the therapist–patient relationship reaches its limits and therapists are required to set boundaries, or when the relationship itself risks further undermining interpersonal trust.

As described in the previous section, the various diminutions of emotional abilities in BPD may translate into significant difficulties in enacting certain forms of trust. Most importantly, such struggles in a given situation can appear unmotivated to people without a BPD diagnosis. For the latter, because they possess greater fiduciary capacities, the question of whom, what, and how to trust may not arise thematically at all, whereas those with limited fiduciary capacities require much greater interpersonal assurance, explicit commitment, and validation in order to quiet skeptical or suspicious inner voices.

It is also important to recognize that people with BPD sometimes engage in strategies intended to reduce insecurity and to discern how others—including clinicians and practitioners—are positioned toward them. These strategies are not seldom perceived by others as manipulative or as presenting challenges that are difficult to handle (Schmidt 2021b). Because people with BPD “do tend to push people’s buttons” (Potter 2006, 149), such strategies can involve others emotionally more than they wish and may lead to deep frustration. As a result, clinicians and practitioners may be inclined to turn their backs on individuals with BPD—whether in subtle yet still noticeable ways, or through more explicit forms of distancing, avoidance, detachment, disengagement, termination of the therapeutic relationship, or stigmatization—all of which intensify the person’s experience of rejection.

Because individuals with BPD belong to the group of patients who may push clinicians and practitioners to their own psychological limits in the provision of care, it is necessary to identify ways for therapists to set boundaries while minimizing the emotional impact on those struggling with BPD. Since the setting of boundaries is often perceived as a form of abandonment—and thus as a disappointment of interpersonal trust—it is crucial that this be done in ways that enable the person with BPD to enact alternative forms of trust.

Hence, I propose that the treatment of individuals with BPD should always include various opportunities or supports to help them activate alternative fiduciary capacities. Precisely because individuals with BPD often struggle with low self-confidence and a lack of interpersonal trust, it is especially important to support them in finding alternative ways of living trustfully in the world whenever trust in the therapeutic relationship—inevitably, at times—feels undermined.

This might, after all, prove to be an important component of therapy in BPD. While it is typically assumed that interpersonal trust in people with BPD can be repaired through the therapeutic relationship, indicating and supporting alternative ways to strengthen fiduciary capacities that are not reliant on the connection to practitioners may help individuals with BPD fortify their trust-structures and provide an essential complement to therapy. At times, it may indeed be crucial that trust in self, others, and the world is learned and restored through the emotional connection with therapists and the dynamics involved. However, experiencing that one can maintain a trusting attitude even in the face of rejection, abandonment, or the simple absence of desired interpersonal goods can also constitute an important step toward building trust-structures beyond interpersonal trust and achieving greater independence from others.

Precisely because individuals with BPD often struggle with fragile self-confidence and impaired trust, it becomes an ethical as well as a professional imperative for practitioners to cultivate conditions in which some modality of trust or self-efficacy can be realized. In doing so, they provide opportunities for patients to restore confidence—if not primarily in the

therapeutic relationship, then at least in their own agency and capacity for self-determination. How healthcare professionals can create such opportunities while simultaneously maintaining appropriate boundaries is an important challenge that calls for further conceptual, phenomenological, and empirical analysis. Given the central importance of trust-structures in the genesis and maintenance of BPD—and of other mental health conditions—such analyses appear both promising and worthwhile. They would certainly help identify the conditions and practices through which psychiatric and psychotherapeutic treatment can foster moral growth (cf. Moskalewicz et al. 2025).

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